

Diagnostic Contribution of the FilmArray® Gastrointestinal Panel in Infectious Gastroenteritis: A Five-Year Retrospective Study in a Moroccan Military Hospital

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Abstract :

Accurate and rapid diagnosis of infectious gastroenteritis is essential for effective management. The FilmArray® Gastrointestinal Panel is a multiplex PCR system that enables the simultaneous detection of 22 enteropathogens from a single stool sample. The aim of this study was to evaluate the diagnostic contribution of the FilmArray® Gastrointestinal Panel in patients suspected of having infectious gastroenteritis at the Avicenne Military Hospital in Marrakech.

This retrospective study was conducted on 110 stool samples collected between 2020 and 2025. The overall positivity rate was 55.4%, with bacteria accounting for 86% of the pathogens detected, followed by viruses (11.2%) and parasites (2.8%). *Escherichia coli* pathovars were the most frequently identified. Co-infections were detected in 42.6% of positive samples. The median turnaround time for FilmArray® results was 7 hours and 25 minutes, compared with 51 hours for stool cultures.

The FilmArray® gastrointestinal panel has considerably improved the speed and extent of pathogen detection in cases of infectious gastroenteritis. Its capacity to identify co-infections and underdiagnosed pathogens highlights its diagnostic value. However, interpretation must

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be guided by the clinical context, and close collaboration between clinician and laboratory remains essential for optimal use.

Keywords : *Gastroenteritis ; Multiplex PCR ; Enteropathogens ; Syndromic testing ; Molecular diagnostic*

Introduction :

Gastroenteritis is an inflammation of the digestive tract that causes a variety of symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, diarrhea, fever, and, in severe cases, dehydration (Malbos, 2023). Predominantly of infectious origin, it can be caused by viruses, bacteria, parasites, or more rarely, fungi. Common worldwide, it represents a public health concern, particularly in developing countries where it severely affects children, but also in industrialized countries, where it accounts for a significant number of medical consultations (Elliott, 2007).

The diagnosis of gastroenteritis is most often based on clinical presentation. Microbiological tests are not systematic, and their indication depends on the epidemiological context and patient-specific risk factors. However, conventional tests have limitations in terms of sensitivity, specificity, and turnaround time (Mariani-Kurkdjian et al., 2016). These constraints have favored the emergence of molecular techniques such as multiplex PCR, which are better suited to current clinical needs.

In this context, the Gastrointestinal (GI) FilmArray® panel (BioFire Diagnostics, bioMérieux) represents a significant advancement in the field of microbiological diagnosis of infectious gastroenteritis. It is an automated system based on real-time multiplex PCR, allowing simultaneous and rapid detection of multiple bacterial, viral, or parasitic enteropathogens from a single stool sample, without any prior extraction or culture step (« Référentiel des examens », s. d.).

The present study aims to evaluate the contribution of the Gastrointestinal FilmArray® panel in the diagnosis of infectious gastroenteritis at the Avicenne Military Hospital in Marrakech.

Materials and Methods:

1. Type and location of the study:

This is a retrospective descriptive study conducted in the microbiology laboratory of the Avicenne Military Hospital in Marrakech. The study involved 110 stool samples collected between March 2020 and March 2025.

2. Study population:

Participants were hospitalized patients or outpatients presenting symptoms suggestive of infectious gastroenteritis.

2.1. Inclusion criteria :

Patients were included if they were hospitalized or seen in consultation during the study period, presented at least three of the following symptoms: diarrhea, abdominal pain, vomiting, nausea, fever, or anorexia and underwent stool analysis by FilmArray® that was medically justified.

2.2. Exclusion criteria :

Excluded cases were diarrhea of dietary origin or secondary to antibiotic therapy, cases related to endocrine pathology or food allergy and redundant samples.

3. Sampling procedures:

Samples were collected following the recommendations outlined in the Guide to Good Laboratory Practices (Arrêté relatif au guide de bonne exécution des analyses de biologie médicale, 2010). Strict hygiene protocols were observed throughout the process. Each specimen was obtained using a sterile, clearly labeled container indicating the patient's name, surname, date and time of collection, clinical indication, and any ongoing treatments. Samples

were transported to the laboratory within two hours of collection; if delays occurred, specimens were stored at 4°C for no longer than 24 hours prior to analysis.

4. Microbiological analysis:

Stool samples were analyzed using the Gastrointestinal (GI) FilmArray® panel (BioFire Diagnostics, bioMérieux), designed to simultaneously detect 22 pathogens responsible for infectious gastroenteritis, including bacteria, viruses, and parasites. Results, available in approximately one hour, indicated the presence or absence of a detectable signal for each pathogen.

5. Data analysis:

Clinical and microbiological data were collected from the laboratory's electronic records, patient hospitalization files included in the study, and biological test forms for outpatients. All data were then processed and analyzed Microsoft Excel 2021 software for data entry, statistical description, and generation of tables and graphs.

6. Ethical considerations:

All clinical and biological data collected for this study were anonymized at the time of collection and used solely for scientific analysis purposes. No direct or indirect patient identification was possible based on the presented results.

Results :

The study involved 110 patients who underwent stool sampling for the detection of enteropathogenic agents. Among these patients, 69 were male (62.7%) and 41 were female (37.3%), resulting in a male-to-female ratio of 1.68, reflecting a clear male predominance in the studied population.

Out of the 110 samples analyzed, 61 tested positive for at least one pathogen, corresponding to a positivity rate of 55.4%. In total, 106 pathogens were identified in these samples. Among

the detected agents, bacteria accounted for the majority of cases at 86% ($n = 91$), followed by viruses (11.2%, $n = 12$) and parasites (2.8%, $n = 3$) (Figure 1).

Figure 1 : Distribution of identified pathogens by type

Regarding bacterial agents, enteropathogenic *Escherichia coli* (EPEC) was the most frequently detected (24.5%, $n = 26$), followed by enteroaggregative *Escherichia coli* (EAEC) (16%, $n = 17$), *Salmonella* (9.5%, $n = 10$), shiga-like toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC) (8.5%, $n = 9$), enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC) and Shigella/enteroinvasive *Escherichia coli* (EIEC) (7.5% each, $n = 8$), *Campylobacter* (6.6%, $n = 7$), *Clostridium difficile* (4%, $n = 4$), and *Plesiomonas shigelloides* (1.9%, $n = 2$). No cases of *Vibrio cholerae* or *Yersinia enterocolitica* were detected.

For the viruses, Norovirus GI/GII was the main detected agent (6.6%, $n = 7$), followed by Rotavirus A (1.9%, $n = 2$), while Astrovirus, Adenovirus F 40/41 and Sapovirus were each found in a single sample (0.9% each, $n = 1$).

Regarding parasites, *Giardia lamblia* was detected in two samples (1.9%) and *Cryptosporidium* in one case (0.9%). No other parasites included in the panel were identified.

Analysis of co-infections showed that among the 61 positive samples, 35 (57.4%) corresponded to mono-infections, while 26 (42.6%) were co-infections. Among the latter, 16 cases (26.2%) involved two pathogens, 5 cases (8.2%) involved three pathogens, 2 cases (3.2%) involved four pathogens, one case (0.9%) involved five pathogens, and another case (0.9%) involved six pathogens (Figure 2).

Figure 2 : Distribution of co-infections by number of pathogens.

Finally, the median turnaround time for results using the FilmArray® technology was 7 hours and 25 minutes, although the analytical phase lasts only about one hour. This delay accounts for various logistical steps (sample transport, registration, cassette preparation, results validation) and the prioritization of more urgent analyses within the laboratory workflow. For comparison, the average turnaround time for results by stool culture was 51 hours in the same department.

Discussion :

This study allowed us to explore the contribution of this innovative molecular biology method, capable of simultaneously detecting 22 enteropathogenic agents, and to assess its

potential impact on the diagnostic and clinical management of patients at the Avicenne Military Hospital in Marrakech.

We observed a male predominance, with 62.7% of patients being male compared to 37.3% female, resulting in a male-to-female ratio of 1.68. This predominance generally aligns with several data reported in the literature. Indeed, the study by Piralla *et al.* (Piralla *et al.*, 2017) reported a sex ratio of 1.36, while the study by Khare *et al.* (Khare *et al.*, 2014) showed a nearly balanced distribution between the sexes with a sex ratio of 1.02. These data suggest a slight tendency toward male predominance in the occurrence of infectious gastroenteritis. Conversely, other studies such as those by Buss *et al.* (Buss *et al.*, 2015) and Spina *et al.* (Buss *et al.*, 2015) report a slight female predominance with a sex ratio of 0.86 and 0.90 respectively. These variations across different contexts could be related to socio-behavioral, occupational, or immunological factors influencing exposure to pathogens or medical consultation.

The overall positivity rate obtained using the GI FilmArray® panel was 55.4%, reflecting a satisfactory diagnostic performance in detecting enteropathogenic agents. This result is comparable to that reported in the study by Spina *et al.* (Spina *et al.*, 2015), which documented a positivity rate of 54.2%. However, it remains higher than those reported by Khare *et al.* (Khare *et al.*, 2014) (33.0%) and Murphy *et al.* (40.4%) (Murphy *et al.*, 2017), which could be explained by differences in the studied populations, inclusion criteria, epidemiological contexts, or seasonality of sample collection. These variations highlight the importance of the context in which the GI FilmArray® panel is used and the interpretation of results based on local epidemiological characteristics.

In our study, bacteria represented the vast majority of identified pathogens (86%), confirming their predominant role in infectious gastroenteritis. Among these, diarrheagenic *Escherichia coli* pathovars occupy a central position, accounting for 64% of the detected bacterial pathogens, a proportion significantly higher than that reported in several international studies (Calderaro *et al.*, 2018; Stockmann *et al.*, 2017). The EPEC pathovar was the most frequently identified agent, with a positivity rate of 24.5%, confirming findings from other studies where

EPEC also ranks among the dominant pathogens (Buss et al., 2015; Khare et al., 2014; Piralla et al., 2017; Spina et al., 2015). However, this rate is higher than in some series, notably Murphy *et al.* (Murphy et al., 2017), where EPEC ranked third after *Clostridium difficile* and Norovirus. Literature also highlights frequent cases of asymptomatic carriage, raising questions about its true responsibility in symptomatology. Further studies on virulence factors and clinical context are needed to better interpret its detection. The EAEC pathovar was the second most common pathogen in our series (16%). Several studies, such as that by Nataro *et al.* (Nataro et al., 2006), have shown a significant association between EAEC and digestive symptoms, although asymptomatic carriage remains possible. This observation underscores the need for cautious interpretation of results, taking the clinical context into account.

We identified 10 cases of *Salmonella* (9.5%), placing this agent third among the detected bacteria. This frequency is higher than that reported in some recent studies, where *Salmonella* no longer ranks among the main detected agents (7th to 9th position) (Buss et al., 2015; Murphy et al., 2017; Spina et al., 2015). This result could be related to seasonal factors, isolated contamination episodes, or to the greater sensitivity of the FilmArray® technique used in our study, which allows detection of cases that may have gone unnoticed by conventional methods.

Other *E. coli* pathovars were also detected. The STEC pathovar is a feared pathogen due to its complications, notably hemolytic uremic syndrome. Its rate in our study (8.5%) is higher than in others (2.5% to 3.9%) (Stockmann et al., 2017).. The ETEC and Shigella/EIEC pathovars were each found at 7.5% in our study, a rate higher than those reported in some studies (1.8% to 4.2%) (Piralla et al., 2017; Spina et al., 2015), which could be related to our smaller sample size.

Detected in 6.6% of the samples, *Campylobacter* occupies a modest position in our study, unlike the global literature where it is often cited as the leading cause of acute bacterial gastroenteritis (Guarino et al., 2014). However, this rate is close to that reported in the study by Piralla *et al.* (10.7%) (Piralla et al., 2017), but much higher than in studies such as those by Khare *et al.* and Murphy *et al.* (Khare et al., 2014; Murphy et al., 2017), where detection rates

did not exceed 3%. This result may be explained by geographic and seasonal variations in the prevalence of *Campylobacter*.

In our study, *Clostridium difficile* was identified in 4% of samples, a rate significantly lower than those reported in other studies. Indeed, *Clostridium difficile* accounted for 15.2% of cases in the study by Murphy *et al.* (Murphy *et al.*, 2017), and 17.2% in that of Buss *et al.* (Buss *et al.*, 2015). This difference may be explained by several factors: a smaller patient sample compared to the two studies, lower local circulation of *Clostridium difficile*, or more limited use of specific analyses in suggestive clinical presentations. Furthermore, interpreting results for *Clostridium difficile* remains challenging, particularly in cases of asymptomatic carriage, which is often observed in hospital settings.

Regarding *Plesiomonas shigelloides*, our study identified 1.9% positive cases, a rate comparable to those reported by Murphy *et al.* (1.2%) (Murphy *et al.*, 2017) and Buss *et al.* (1.52%) (Buss *et al.*, 2015). Although this bacterium remains a rare cause of gastroenteritis, especially in temperate regions, its detection via the FilmArray® panel highlights the value of multiplex techniques in identifying emerging or atypical agents often underestimated by conventional methods.

No cases of *Vibrio cholerae* or *Yersinia enterocolitica* were identified. These absences may reflect a low local prevalence. This also confirms the epidemiological relevance of the GI FilmArray® panel, which remains sensitive but must be interpreted in conjunction with the clinical context.

In our study, viruses accounted for 11.2% of the identified pathogens. Norovirus was the main virus detected, with a positivity rate of 6.6%. Literature data have reported rates ranging from 5.7% to 13.9% in the study by Khare *et al.* (Khare *et al.*, 2014), 8.9% in Murphy *et al.* (Murphy *et al.*, 2017), and 3.8% in Buss *et al.* . These variations may be explained by differences in epidemiological context, seasonality, or the target population in each study.

Regarding Rotavirus, we observed a low positivity rate of 1.9%, which contrasts with higher rates reported in the literature: 14.5% in the study by Calderaro *et al.* (Calderaro *et al.*, 2018)

and 4% in Stockmann *et al.* (Stockmann et al., 2017). This difference could be attributed to several factors. First, our study was conducted mainly on an adult population, whereas Rotavirus is primarily found in children. Second, the introduction of Rotavirus vaccination in Morocco could also explain the reduced circulation of the virus in the general population.

Other viruses were detected at low frequency, notably Adenovirus, Sapovirus, and Astrovirus, each with a rate of 0.9%. Although rarely identified, their role in viral gastroenteritis should not be overlooked. In particular, Sapovirus is often underdiagnosed because it is not included in conventional diagnostic methods. Studies such as Murphy *et al.* (Murphy et al., 2017) report a rate of 2%, while others, like Calderaro and Stockmann (Calderaro et al., 2018; Stockmann et al., 2017), report higher rates ranging from 8.2% to 8.8%.

These results highlight the value of a syndromic approach, such as that offered by the FilmArray® GI panel, which allows simultaneous detection of viruses rarely sought by conventional methods, thereby reinforcing the usefulness of this technology for rapid and comprehensive etiological management of infectious gastroenteritis.

In our study, *Giardia lamblia* was identified in two cases, corresponding to a positivity rate of 1.9%. This cosmopolitan protozoan, although more frequently encountered in children, can also be found in adults, as demonstrated by our series. In a similar study, only one case was detected using FilmArray® technology, compared to no detections by conventional stool parasitological examination (Hilmoine, 2018). These results highlight the superior sensitivity of the FilmArray® method, particularly in detecting parasites often underestimated by conventional techniques.

In addition to the two cases of *Giardia lamblia*, one case of *Cryptosporidium* was identified in our study, representing a rate of 0.9%. This parasite is also recognized for its role in gastroenteritis, especially in epidemic contexts or among immunocompromised individuals. Its detection in our general population illustrates the FilmArray® panel's ability to identify parasitic agents that are often overlooked or difficult to detect by routine examinations.

In our study, co-infections were identified in 42.6% of the positive samples, a relatively high rate compared to what has been reported in the literature. Indeed, several multicenter studies report co-infection rates ranging from 19.3% to 32.5% (Buss et al., 2015; Calderaro et al., 2018; Khare et al., 2014; Murphy et al., 2017; Piralla et al., 2017). Others, such as Stockmann *et al.* (Stockmann et al., 2017), found a lower overall rate (15%), though it reached 21% in children under five years old. Similarly, co-infection rates are generally lower in adult populations, as indicated by studies from Spina *et al.* (16.4%) (Spina et al., 2015) and Buss *et al.* (16.8%) (Buss et al., 2015).

The high rate observed in our series could be explained by several factors, notably the enhanced sensitivity of the FilmArray® technology, which enables the simultaneous detection of multiple pathogens from a single sample. It is also possible that an initial infection disrupts the intestinal microbiota balance, promoting secondary colonization by other pathogens, particularly enterobacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, as suggested by several authors (Lupp et al., 2007; Murphy et al., 2017).

These findings highlight the significant, and likely underestimated, role of co-infections in acute gastroenteritis, which are often not identified by conventional methods (Buss et al., 2015). However, their clinical relevance remains to be clarified, particularly in cases where multiple enteropathogens are detected simultaneously, such as EPEC or EAEC, whose pathogenicity depends on the clinical context and the patient's underlying condition.

In our study, the median turnaround time for results with FilmArray® was 7 hours and 25 minutes, compared to 51 hours for conventional stool culture. These results are consistent with other studies (Hilmoine, 2018; Murphy et al., 2017), confirming one of the major advantages of the FilmArray® GI panel: its speed. This time-saving significantly improves patient management, especially for bacteriological and parasitological analyses, which are often time-consuming in routine diagnostics. It also allows for faster targeting of pathogens, reduces the risk of missed viral detections, and facilitates patient discharge with complete results, minimizing the need for post-hospitalization recalls.

Conclusion :

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Our study evaluated the contribution of the multiplex PCR syndromic approach (FilmArray® GI Panel) in diagnosing acute gastroenteritis within our institution. This method enabled rapid and simultaneous detection of a broad range of pathogens from a single stool sample by significantly reducing turnaround times. It also revealed a notable rate of co-infections, often missed by conventional methods, raising questions about their clinical relevance in the absence of quantification or pathogen viability data. While the multiplex PCR approach is a powerful diagnostic tool, its results must be interpreted within a comprehensive clinical context. Close collaboration between clinicians and microbiologists remains essential for appropriate use and interpretation.

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Conflicts of interest :

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

Informed Consent :

Informed consent was obtained from participants.

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